

Differences and Similarities in the Political Participation, between China and South Korea

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Abstract: This paper aims to analyse political participation in China and South Korea. Additionally, through this research, we will try to find the answer to the Research Question. Furthermore, this research expects to find similar types of political participation in both countries and different attitudes from the governments against people's political participation. According to my understanding the Political participation concept, refers to how people can be existing in political actions, it could be through political parties and organized political movements or elections, it also existed as a street form of political participation, by individuals against some political decisions or governmental system. Political participation also shows people's participation and how people influence the policymaking process. This paper will discuss the case of citizens' political participation and its limits for the Chinese communist party and its counterpart South Korea. In the first instance, we will start by defining the main concept of this research, which is political participation.

Keywords: political participation, China, South Korea.

1. Introduction

In all countries, citizens should have a space to express their thoughts, opinions and participate in their country to have a better life by achieving their needs. This space is called political participation. Citizens' participation is different from one country to another. Moreover, the important reason for how people know these differences is comparing their state, politics, economic, and state power with other countries. According to many things in this comparison, people's demand has changed. The main reason why people and governments have changed and developed their demands and political, cultural, social, and economic sectors, is comparing their condition and political structure, norms... with other countries whether it is similar to their structure or different. To understand their situation they need to compare it with other countries.

To understand one state system we need to compare it with other state systems. This essay discusses the comparison between China and South Korea political participation, to highlight the main differences and similarities in each political participation. Through different political participation whether it is legal participation or illegal participation, choosing the countries was because both have different political system, and

different backgrounds which will be explained later in the research.

Political participation steep according to the state structure. China is a communist party-state. Their political participation is different from the liberal democratic state. On the other hand, South Korea is a presidential representative democratic republic. Both have different political participation actions according to their state system.

The only common relation that we know, is that both states are in Asia, both are productive at some point. For more information about their political participation, this research will try to find answers through analysing both political participations.

Political participation "is any number of voluntary activities undertaken by the public to influence public policy either directly or by affecting the selection of persons who make those policies. Though typically associated with voting in elections, political participation includes activities such as working on political campaigns, donating money to candidates or causes, contacting public officials, petitioning, protesting, and working with other people on issues."¹

(What Is Political Participation? Definition and Examples, By Robert Longley Published on September 20, 2021, <https://www.thoughtco.com/political-participation-definition-examples-5198236>) Political participation is representing the level of how much the citizen can be active in their political system and decisions.

Research Hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1: Differences and similarities between China's political participation and South Korea.

Hypothesis 2: The impact of political participation on the citizen in each country.

Political participation has been measured by using dependent variables, using two types of political participation, acceptable and unacceptable. Using two different case studies, China and South Korea.

2. Methodology

For this research, we will start with historical background

¹ What Is Political Participation? Definition and Examples, By Robert Longley Published on September 20, 2021

<https://www.thoughtco.com/political-participation-definition-examples-5198236>

about countries' political participation, then analyse their participation through using history and citizen actions as a case example. In this research, we will try to know more about the differences and similarities in the political systems in China and South Korea political participation and what are their political participation limits and types? to answer these questions and for this research, we will be using the descriptive research method.

To complete this research, we will use the case study method. The case study of Chinese political participation, and South Korean political participation.

Descriptive research :'' refers to the methods that describe the characteristics of the variables under study. This methodology focuses on answering questions relating to ''what'' than the ''why'' of the research subject. The primary focus of descriptive research is to simply describe the nature of the demographics under study instead of focusing on the ''why''.²

3. Literature Review

In order to achieve this research, in the first instance we need to look into the historical background of each country political system, knowing their system will help us realize what kind of participation both have. For China political system we looked into the (BBC, China's political system and the extent of democratic participation China is a communist country governed by one political party that allows only limited democratic activity), then to explain the political participation in China, and how the system works we used (Political Participation in Communist China By James R. Townsend). On the other hand the same stratege was used with explaining South Korea system (History of South Korea, 10 January 2018 by Rosie Tanabe). Moreover to know how the political participation system in South Korea we use Articles about their system (Electoral Politics in South Korea Aurel Croissant).

Forethemore, to have more information and better understanding to the research we used some Articles to explain the political participation types in both countries and how msuch people are involve in the political participation process. For China political participation Types, and how we used (Politics in China, Melanie Manion), in the other hand, as the same for South Korea some Articles, Journals are used to explain their political participation types (The Quality of Social Capital and Political Participation in South Korea Author(s): Aie-Rie Lee Source Journal of East Asian Studies 3 (September–December 2010, Cambridge University Press).

Literature review focuses on how much the government open the chance for citizen to be part of the political participation and policy making process through the political participation. (Why Are Street Protests So Common in South Korea? South Korea's culture of protest is a reflection of an engaged public.

By Drananda Rohimone and Grant Wyeth August 15, 2019), (Politics in China, Melanie Manion). Also we will focus on highlighting the differences and similarities between both countries political participation, according to their different political system, and the different ways of how the government treat their citizen.

4. China Political Participation

The first instance will began with background of the political system in China and China's political participation. Officially titled the People's Republic of China, China has the highest population of any country on Earth. The state took control of the factories, businesses, the land etc, on behalf of the people. There was no private ownership. The Communist Party of China (CPC) took control and the people worked on behalf of the common good. According to Mao, the idea of individual progress at the expense of others was not acceptable.³ (BBC, Chinas political system and the extent of democratic participation, part of modern studies, World power China). The communist state established in Peking 1949, was strictly speaking, defined as a peoples emocratic dictatorship, rather than a dictatorship of the proletariat.⁴ (James R. Townsed, Political participation in the communist party, Cambridge University, (162-163).

Since China is represented by Communist part state, which is the main and only authority in China all the decisions are taking just by the communist part. The Chinese leaders see that only by the communist party China will developed and the western democracy will cause only coorruption in politics, culture, economic sectors in China.⁵ Democratic system will open the chance for citizen to participate more in the state, so China prefers to have one and only party that controls all the state system rather than open the chance for other parties or authorities to be participation in the political process.

Chinese citizens want to be more involved in the political process since it is the primary factor affecting all other sectors. The reason is that China is one party that dominates the country and the people. So there is no opportunity for different leaders with different thoughts, beliefs to participate or be part of the politics in China. Citizens which have opposing demands and beliefs want to be part of their system and change some of their policies, through having the chance to participate in the political sector to speak up for their concerns by political participation. What are the political participation types in the Chinese Communist party?

Political Participation, Communist party state has different political participation from the liberal democratic system, Communist part has different type of relations between leader and citizen, it claims to represent the intersts of their citizen, so

² Descriptive Research: Definition, Method and Examples
Exclusive Step by Step guide to Descriptive Research
<https://www.voxco.com/blog/descriptive-research/>

³ *China's political system and the extent of democratic participation*
China is a communist country governed by one political party that allows only limited democratic activity. Part of Modern Studies. World power:
China <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/zbhnrj6/revision/3>

⁴ Political Participation in Communist China by James R. Townsend

⁵ *China's political institutions and government decision-making While the Communist Party controls everyday life in China, there are territories where its powers and decision-making is challenged. Part of Modern Studies*
World power: China <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/zbhnrj6/revision/3>

they don't need any other party to represent it.⁶ The communist party of state have different roles and political relations between citizen, society and government, these differences in the relations also affect how people participate in the state, how much the citizen can intervene and participate in the political process.

According to (Melanie Manion, politics in China) there are two major political participation in China. Acceptable political participation, and unacceptable political participation.

In the first instance we need to know what is the definition of the Acceptable political participation and unacceptable political participation. In my point of view, Acceptable political participation: is the legal participation for the citizen under the government control and limitation and it may be confined in elections or contact directly with the government by the legal Organization.

On the other hand unacceptable participation is the illegal participation according to the government, which happens by the individuals or organized movements in order to achieve and highlight their interests and needs that they cannot achieve it with the legal Participation.

The primary of political participation is election, Communist party state also has election, but it's different than any other election process, communist party elections is with very rigorous system. Elections in China have a hierarchical selection system, which aim to take the local election, then national people's congress. Then the people congress elects the prime minister's popularity governments. All under the control of the Communist party. On the other hand, there is no election for the Chinese president, because China is a Communist party state, so they control the election process but without have an official presidential election according to the state system.

Acceptable political participation according to (Melanie Manion, politics in China) confine three main changes in the participations. Primarily, Changes in Rule is one of the important aspects of political participation particularly and politics in general, changing in rule played a huge role in developing and affecting other aspects in China. It's also helped to decrease burden of Chinese citizen, Communist party claim that if they want to develop their economy they need in the first instance a stable politics and changes in rule is a great start to achieve it.⁷ Changes in rule was one of the primary movements occur in the political cooperation framework for the Chinese individuals which open the opportunity for the Chinese to partake in political cases, what makes interest routine and without burdens on the Chinese. They changed the participation for open the chance for the citizen to be part of the political process, by participating in political activities given by the Communist party state and not participating is not accepting the Communist party. Through this participation they claim that they limit the political interference in the Chinese citizens lives. But in my opinion still is controlling the citizen's lives through

giving them a controlled space of political participation by the Communist party boundary.

Local Congress Elections: another way of the political participation in China is the Local congress elections. Candidates have been chosen by elections and not secret ballot, in the local elections they were elected directly, but the electors were not ordinary Chinese. On the other hand new law for local elections have been applied in 1979 states that local election have to be secret elections and the candidates number should be more than the representative number, even if its secret election, still some of the candidates lose because they do not fill what citizen expect from their representative. Through these election Communist party control their representative, and on the other hand its away to know what the Citizen interest and demand through which candidate they choose and to not allow any opposition for the Communist party state.⁸

Village Committees: China has gradually implemented the village autonomy system, which interest all the citizens who are students to social, economical, and political, also the election regime and structure, the village committees open the chance for more democracy and self determination, even if its just a village committee and it not playing a huge role, but still it is a great start for more democracy and more decision makers to participate in the village committees.⁹ Also it more than opening the chance for taking their own decisions and participate, it played a role in developing the system. In my opinion this kind of participation also open the chance for the communist party to know and realize what kind of thought and believes the citizens have. It's not just a try to act democratic but it has an important impact of giving the citizens a space to show their interests to be controlled later on by the communist party. This kind of participation, more than it affects the citizens, its in the first instance for achieving the system goals.

"creating a representative assembly (at least in some villages) and a system of "democratic oversight", which essentially amounts to stressing transparency and accountability in the political life of the village, and developing a functional division of labor among village committee members"¹⁰ (Jorgen Elklit, The Chinese village committee electoral system, March 1, 1997, University of Aarhus, Denmark, (3-5).

According to the information given in this research, the reforms that happen in the acceptable political participation are only participation in a local and limitation given by the communist party and under its controlled by them to avoid any anarchy.

Unacceptable political participation:

Different type of political participation, which is happen by the Chinese citizen to protest in the streets, strikes, and reform against certain decisions or actions of the state is political participation for the citizens, but it unacceptable political

⁶ Politics in China, Melanie Manion, Week_12_Reading_Text_China.pdf

⁷ Politics in China, Melanie Manion, Week_12_Reading_Text_China.pdf

⁸ Politics in China, Melanie Manion, Week_12_Reading_Text_China.pdf

⁹ The Chinese Village Committee Electoral System Jorgen Elklit First Published March 1, 1997 Research Article, Department of Political Science, University of Aarhus, Denmark

¹⁰ The Chinese Village Committee Electoral System Jorgen Elklit First Published March 1, 1997 Research Article <https://doi.org/10.1177/0920203X9701100401> Department of Political Science, University of Aarhus, Denmark

participation for the Chinese communist regime. Citizens of China are seeing that this kind of participation is more effective for them than the control participation with the state regime control and restrictions.

Different sorts of “officially unacceptable” political participation have different explanations, but none can be explained without reference to the post Mao reforms. On the one hand, economic reforms have produced some socially unacceptable outcomes: more (and more visible) inflation, unemployment, crime, and corruption, for example. Rural unrest has typically been triggered by local corruption and exaction of excessive (often illegal) taxes and fees. Urban unrest strikes, slowdowns, and demonstrations has increased too, as state enterprises struggle to survive in the socialist market economy.¹¹ (Melanie Manion, *Politics in China*, (431-436)

This kind of participation came as a result of a governmental decisions and policies which is complete on the citizens. Also because their legal participation is limited people resort to this sort of participation.

According to Melanie Manion, the unacceptable political participation must uphold four fundamental principles, official view was made clear in 1979. That political participation must uphold: (1) the socialist road. (2) Marxism–Leninism–Mao Zedong Thought. (3) The people’s democratic dictatorship. (4) the leadership of the Communist Party.¹² (Melanie Manion, *Politics in China*, (431-436)

Protesters and Reformers: For a historical information about China protests and reforms. There are three main protests in Chinese history. The main one which brought millions of Chinese into Tiananmen Square were the third major political protest movement since Mao’s death. The first was in 1978 and 1979, the second in 1986 and 1987. All three were officially unacceptable; all were linked in some important way to official reforms and reformers, and all ended in failure for mass protesters. Protests are officially unacceptable mainly because of their form of expression. The official consensus since December 1978 has been that the most important priority for China is economic growth, with social order and stability as prerequisites for growth. Mass protests are distinctly disorderly. Further, as a form of political participation, mass protests are a symptom of regime failure in two senses. By turning to the streets to articulate their demands, protesters demonstrate that official channels for expressing critical views are not working and that they do not believe the Communist Party’s claim that it can correct its own mistakes. Further, protesters are clearly not alienated from politics.¹³

Protests are not acceptable for the communist state because it sort of expressing the citizens interests and needs, and some of citizens needs are affecting the system itself. For this purpose the Communist state opens the chance for the citizen to participate through some special channels formed specially to this purpose. However the citizens found it not enough for their

participation¹⁴. In my point of view, according to this study this way was not enough for the Chinese people to use it in order to address their opinion and the changes that they want, because of this Chinese citizen like any other nation who saw that the perfect way of pressure on the government is through going in streets and protest. Also through the development Chinese used the media as a way to express their demands and opposition, it is a space that they can use it in order to make their voices heard without the government limits and restrictions.

5. South Korea Political Participation

In this section we will talk about South Korea political participation, first of all we will start with a basic information about South Korea political system. The Constitution of the Republic of Korea calls for a liberal democratic political system. Its principles are based on the sovereignty of the people, with all the authority of state emanating from its citizens: Separation of powers among the three branches of government, the rule of law, and the responsibility to promote citizens’ welfare, as well as the attainment of a peaceful unification of Korea. President Every five years, Korean citizens above the age of 20 elect the President in a nationwide, direct, equal and secret ballot. The President is the head of the executive branch and represents the nation externally. The President serves a single five-year term, with no additional term allowed. The current constitution, which was hammered out by a consensus among the ruling and opposition parties in 1987, stipulates the single five-year term provision as a safeguard against any individual holding the government power for a protracted period of time. Under the current political system, the President plays several major roles. First, the President is head of state, leading the government and representing the nation in foreign relations. The president has the duty to uphold the constitution and protect and preserve national independence and territorial integrity, as well as to carry out the unique task of attaining a peaceful unification of Korea. The President is the Chief Executive of government. In this capacity, he enforces the laws passed by the legislature and issues orders and decrees for that purpose. He is also the commander-in-chief of the armed forces, and has exclusive authority over military policies, including the power to declare war.¹⁵ (One world nations online, *Korean political system, South Korea*.)

The President performs his executive functions through the State Council, or the Cabinet made up of 15 to 30 members, whom he appoints upon the recommendation of the Prime Minister. However, the President is solely responsible for all important government policies. The Prime Minister is appointed by the President and approved by the National Assembly. The members of the State Council, or the Cabinet, lead and supervise their administrative ministries, participate in the deliberation of major state affairs, and act on behalf of the President.¹⁶ (One world nations online, *Korean political*

¹¹ *Politics in China*, Melanie Manion, *Week_12_Reading_Text_China.pdf*

¹² *Politics in China*, Melanie Manion, *Week_12_Reading_Text_China.pdf*

¹³ *Politics in China*, Melanie Manion, *Week_12_Reading_Text_China.pdf*

¹⁴ *Politics in China*, Melanie Manion, *Week_12_Reading_Text_China.pdf*

¹⁵ One world nations online, *Korean political system, South Korea*. https://www.nationsonline.org/oneworld/korea_south_profile.htm

¹⁶ One world nations online, *Korean political system, South Korea*. https://www.nationsonline.org/oneworld/korea_south_profile.htm

system, South Korea.)

History of South Korea formally begins with the establishment of South Korea in 1948. South Korea, known as one of the four tigers of Asia, has risen from the rubble of the Korean War into one of the world's foremost economies and vibrant democracies. South Korea's history has been marked by alternating periods of democratic and autocratic rule. Historians have conventionally numbered civilian governments from the First Republic of Syngman Rhee to the contemporary Sixth Republic. The First Republic, arguably democratic at its inception, became increasingly autocratic until its collapse in 1960. The Second Republic, strongly democratic, suffered an overthrow in less than a year, with an autocratic military regime taking power. The Third, Fourth, and Fifth Republics, while nominally democratic, have been widely regarded as the continuation of military rule. With the Sixth Republic, the country has gradually stabilized into a liberal democracy.¹⁷ (Rosie Tanabe, *History of South Korea*, January 10, 2018, New World encyclopedia).

What is important in the governmental and political system, is how much people involve in the politics, how much people are participating represent how much the country is democratic. In South Korea the political participation is different than the communist part participation, this chapter will discuss the political participation types and forms in South Korea. South Korea as any other country which has the acceptable and under the government control participation an unacceptable participation, but still there is differences in how the government react and what are the participation limits.

Primarily type of political participation and the most important type are Elections, it's the significant participation for citizen, and through election people can participate and chose their represent, president. In my point of view it's the basic right for the citizens in each country in this Chapter will know if South Korea is using the democratic way of elections. According to the historical information in South Korea election was developed during the years and system development.

Elections was one of the main aspects that South Korea developed and used it to act more democratic; to act more democratic it opens the chance to act more democratic through opening the chance for the authoritarian and opposition parties to participate in the election, because they don't want to infringe the law of democratic elections. However, election is not just system used in the country or for legal or governmental interests, it a way to secure the system. Changing in the election system and regime was a way for the continuity of the regime

and to be more stable.¹⁸

"On the other hand, That social capital encourages political participation in different ways and to varying degrees. In the case of voting, simple Membership is a significant predictor after the effects of other controls enter the picture. It does, however, surprise us to see that neither Commitment nor Interaction has a significant effect on voting. The original assumption was that either political communication with associational fellows or frequent participation in group activities was more likely to generate political participation voting in this case. For whatever reason, it appears that in Korea, talking politics with group members or participating in group meetings is one thing, and participation in elections is another".¹⁹ (Aie Rie Lee, *The Quality of Social Capital and political participation in South Korea*, September- December 2021, by Cambridge University, (498-502).

Candidates use campaign in order to have more supporters, even if it is not a very good way for the political process. However the campaign can help them in their elections and can bring new voters for them.²⁰ In my opinion that campaign is important in the elections process, it can give the citizens an overview of this candidates political system and what kind of policies he has, his political background and what progress he has, then they decide if they have common interests or not. On the other hand campaign are just a way of show, if it is more close to citizens interests and will achieve their need and demands the candidate will win by their voices. Not all of these campaign are achieved in reality.

Moreover, it also important to highlight that there is a relationship between the political participation and associational membership, the associational membership is a way of participating to achieve a common interest, also it creates a relation between citizens, so it enhance citizens political participation."On the one hand, Putnam defined social capital as "features of social organization, such as networks, norms, and social trust that facilitate coordination and cooperation for mutual benefit" A large stock of social capital, such as networks of associational engagement, fosters coordination and communication among citizens, encourages norms of reciprocity and trust, and thus boost citizens' capacity to engage in political actions for collective benefits."²¹ (Hyunrang Han- Lili Wang, *Voluntary Association involvement and political participation in South Korea*, July 7, 2021, (541-543).

Voluntary associations allow to their member through their skills in social and organization skills to participate more in

¹⁷ History of South Korea Author: New World Encyclopedia contributors
Publisher: *New World Encyclopedia*, Date of last revision: 10 January 2018
15:21 UTC Date retrieved: 25 December 2021 22:03 UT Permanent
URL: https://www.newworldencyclopedia.org/p/index.php?title=History_of_South_Korea&oldid=1008692

¹⁸ Electoral Politics in South Korea Aurel Croissant
<https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/iez/01361008.pdf>

¹⁹ The Quality of Social Capital and Political Participation in South Korea
Author(s): Aie-Rie Lee Source: *Journal of East Asian Studies*, SEPTEMBER-

December 2010, Vol. 10, No. 3 (September–December 2010), pp. 483-505
Published by: Cambridge University Press

²⁰ The Quality of Social Capital and Political Participation in South Korea
Author(s): Aie-Rie Lee Source: *Journal of East Asian Studies*, September–
December 2010, Vol. 10, No. 3 (September–December 2010), pp. 483-505
Published by: Cambridge University Press

²¹ Voluntary Association Involvement and Political Participation in South
Korea *Won No, Hyunran Han and Lili Wang* from the journal Nonprofit
Policy Forum, <https://doi.org/10.1515/npf-2021-0002>

politics. Meanwhile they involve the association members in the political activities, because they can affect other citizens to be part and participate. Through these political activities the voluntary association will have more members who believe on it and more participants, consequently, will be more citizens and members involved in the political process.²² On the other hand there is a differences between different type of voluntary association and the level of participation, each type have different level of participation depending on its influence on the citizens and members.

Furthermore, participating in unpolitical organization have the same affect on the political participation process, this type of organization give the members and citizens a chance to know more about their political participation and also involve them more in the political participation, in my opinion this type of participation in the organization gives the citizens a great opportunity to unerstand their political system and way of ruling out of all the political organization because its not conrole by the politics.

Political parties: political parties is also part of the political participation in South Korea citizens can be part of any political party according to their interests and belives. And working to achieve their goal and the party target. Political parties are improvements in the relations between the society and the government.²³

Protests: South Korea like any other country even if they can participate in politics in legal and acceptable way, citizen still use the streets protests to express their opinion and need that they cant achieve it by the othe participations. ubiquity of demonstrations in the streets is to highlight the political culture of South Korea and its is aprimary to realize the relation between the citizens and government. "During South Korea's long period of authoritarian rule (1948-87) protests were seen as the only channel citizens had to express their grievances to the state. However, since the country's reformation as a liberal-democratic society with theoretically a greater ability for interest groups to engage with the state extra-institutional collective action has continued as the primary avenue for the public to convey their interests and concerns. That's partly because, in a hangover from the country's authoritarian period, there is a lack of systematic interaction between the state and the public."²⁴ (Dananda Rohimone-Grant Wyeth, why are street protests so commone in South Jorea culture of protest is a reflection of an engaged public, August 15, 2019).

On the other hand, it's important to highlight that "While democratization has provided citizens with the ability to vote, there remains an absence of adequate mediating institutions within the country, preventing the inclusion of civil society in

the policymaking process. Protest therefore provides a form of quasi-empowerment, giving people a sense of power yet without sophisticated participation in the activities of the state. Although protest is remarkably useful in putting certain issues on the table — and even in removing presidents it falls short of giving civil society the ability to plan, draft, implement, and monitor policies in conjunction with the government"²⁵ (Dananda Rohimone- Grant Wyeth, why are street protests so commone in South Jorea culture of protest is a reflection of an engaged public, August 15, 2019). Even if the country system is trying to achieve all the needs to have a better state, and to be a western democratic state, still there is some need that can't be achieved by lack of some sectors.

6. The Differences and Similarities between China and South Korea Political Participation

According to the research information, both have different system of government. Moreover these different state systems may have some similarities and differences in their political participation, and how much the citizen are involved in the political participation.

The first different is the state system which make any other political participation depening on how the state system will react against or towards it. Chinas communist party state who depends on one party state, and South Korean liberal democratic party state, which is more democratic by making the citizen involve more in politics by the political participation activites. Like what is mentioned in the research how much are citizen involve is how much democratic is the country.

The primary way of political participation is Elections, since both countries have election but each sountry have diferent type and way of organizing the elections. Elections in China are within strict laws and regulations so that they cannot be tampered with, and candidates are not allowed to run in electoral campaigns, but in South Korea, candidates conduct electoral and propaganda campaigns, and the elections are inclusive of all the adult citizen. In China, elections do not include all Mature country members Not all people have the right to vote. The elections in China is unequal elections, becaues the distribution of elections is by regions, so its unequal to prevent all the citizen to involve in the elections and the voting process, and open the chance just for the prevelent party and reion to be participating in elections.

Forthermore,China is one party state, the political parties in china does exist but their involment and affect on the political system and policy making prosecc is not existing comparing by South korea political parties. Political parties in South Korea are existed and represent the citizen interests and ideologies, in

²² Voluntary Association Involvement and Political Participation in South Korea *Won No, Hyunran Han and Lili Wang*

From the journal Nonprofit Policy Forum
<https://doi.org/10.1515/npf-2021-0002>

²³ Why Are Street Protests So Common in South Korea? South Korea's culture of protest is a reflection of an engaged public. By Drananda Rohimone and Grant Wyeth August 15, 2019

²⁴ Why Are Street Protests So Common in South Korea? South Korea's culture of protest is a reflection of an engaged public. By Drananda Rohimone and Grant Wyeth August 15, 2019

²⁵ Why Are Street Protests So Common in South Korea? South Korea's culture of protest is a reflection of an engaged public. By Drananda Rohimone and Grant Wyeth August 15, 2019

my point of view that political parties in South Korea can play a huge role in changing some of the policies that did not suite the citizen demands. Political parties can intervene when the system is not fair for the citizen and if their need an emergence intervene in some law before the elections political parties can play this role. Election held for the political parties to have seats in the national assembly which open the chance for the political parties to intervene in the political, social, culture policies. Political parties in South Korea have huge impact on developing the political participation process depending on each party interest and citizens interests, also it has a special relation with the government.

Local elections are familiar for both China and South Korea, however there is some differences, local elections in China is attempt to take democratic shape but it still not open the opportunity for all the citizen to participate in the local election, according to the information in the first chapter the local elections, people can participate in local elections but the candidates are chosen by the communist party to avoid any participation or representative against them. On the other hand, the local elections in South Korea depend on people participating in elections because South Korea is trying to be more democratic like the western state systems. Involving people participation in local election is part of the democratic process.

In the other hand South Korea have non-political organization, which played a huge role in opening the chance for citizens to participate more, in the case of China and according to the studies this type of organization does not exist in the communist party, to avoid the chaos.

To take everything into account the similarities in the protest's political participation in both China and South Korea is unacceptable participations. Citizens in both countries use the same type of participation against some governmental or cultural systems or norms in order to make their voices heard and try to do some change in the system if all the legal way is not working. Moreover, some of the protests in South Korea are type of the political participation, which is not bind by the government, but it's legal, through these participations' government can understand citizen's demand and need to take them into consideration. Same as China South Korea was having special channels for citizens to participate but they realized that it's not enough for them to participate, protests will achieve the goals they want more than participation in channels formed by the government.

7. Conclusion

To sum up each country has its own political system which controls all the other aspects in the country, culture, social, economic and the most important politics. Each country has its rules and construction with its relationship with the citizen. As we argued in the research political participation is the way that citizen can use it in order to involve in their own political, cultural and social life. Both China and South Korea have different types of political participation and different ways on how the government act towards people participation. Moreover, this information will not be known if we did not

compare these two state system in political participation. These differences between China and South Korea are seen in how much the citizens are accepted their political system and how much they are involved. According to the research we realized that South Korean citizen are more participating than China, the reason is because of the state system South Korea is trying to act more democratic, so in order to be more democratic the citizen participation has a huge impact on how much the country is democratic. In order to answer the research question, we investigated the political participation types, and how much the citizen can be involved in the political actions according to what participations are they allowed to have. Acceptable participations were limited by the government control, so citizens decided to use different way to express their opinions which is the protests, this participation is not acceptable by the government and also have limits in some points. Governments punished and arrested the participants. To conclude, citizen's participation is always controlled by the government and their political system, both examples have different type and limits for the participation but at the end governments do allow to any participation against its rules. Also, we realized that political participation is highly unequal and it common in some nations than the others. We came to the most first point "in order to understand one state system you need to compare it with other state systems" Who know one country know no country. According to all the information mentioned in the research, we can realize that each country has different level of the political participation influenced by the country political system. Each political system opens different way for citizens to participate in their countries. China citizens have a very limit participation type, because all their participation is controlled by the state system so they can't go over it, on the other side we have South Korea their citizens have different types and level of participation because South Korea are trying to act more democratic than China. Because of their political system that opens the chance for South Korean citizens to be involved more in their politics through the different types of participation which give the people the right to be part of the political process.

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